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A review of new strategies to combat malaria resistance: The essential oils approach

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Abstract

Essential oils have been a subject of interest to pharmaceutical researchers for over a century but very recently has evoked much more interests due to their widely reported advantages. One of the advantages of essential oils is the ability to resist and reverse resistance. Malaria is a serious health concern globally with almost half of the world population at risk. Although several investments have been made in antimalarial drugs research and development, malaria continues to pose as a global threat. This is attributable to the high propensity of malaria parasites to develop resistance to the various treatment options. It has however, become important to seek for alternative or new strategies for treating malaria without the risks of malaria resistance. This research is aimed towards reviewing the potentials of harnessing the advantages of essential oils in the treatment of malaria and combating malaria resistance. The various novel drug delivery systems for formulating essentials into dosage forms were also reviewed. It is the view of the authors that the use of essential oils in the treatment of malaria and combating of malaria resistance hold great promises and potentials and therefore recommend that essential oils with scientifically proven antimalarial activity should be formulated as either a nanoemulsion, liposome, NLC, or SLN. This will in addition to protecting the essential oils from rapid degradation, improve their efficacy and effectiveness.

Keywords: Essential oil; Malaria; Resistance; Novel drug delivery systems

1. Introduction

1.1. General overview of Malaria

Malaria is a haematoprotzoan tropical disease resulting from an infection by apicomplexan parasites of the genus *Plasmodium*. The disease is a serious global health problem with nearly half of the world population at risk, over 200 million cases and greater than 400,000 deaths in 2018 alone [1]. Over 90% of malaria deaths occur in the WHO-defined African region, mostly in children less than five years old [1]. Since the dawn of the new millennium in the early 2000s, substantial progress has been made in malaria control. For example, between 2010 and 2018, the incidence rates of malaria have declined by ~19% globally [1]. By 2018, 49 countries had reported less than 10,000 cases up from 40 in 2010 while 27 countries reported fewer than 100 local cases as compared to 17 in 2010 [1]. More importantly, between 2000-2016 the number of countries with endemic malaria has dropped from 106 to 86 while annual mortality rates have declined by over 60% [2]. However, despite these remarkable feats, the disease continues to have a significant impact on people's health and daily livelihoods. This is being recently worsened by the failure of effective control efforts like the emergence of resistance to frontline antimalarial drugs, resistance to insecticides used in vector control and the absence of effective vaccines soon [2,3,4]. More worryingly and the likely consequence of these threats, a global stall in

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malaria control has been recently reported with an observed increase in malaria cases from 2014 to 2016 which has remained at similar levels through to 2018.

1.2. Causative agents

Plasmodium has been identified as the parasite that causes malaria. These parasites are spread to humans through the bites of malaria vectors; infected *Anopheles* female mosquitoes. Four (4) species of Plasmodium parasite infects humans, namely; *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium vivax*, *Plasmodium malariae*, and *Plasmodium ovale*. *P. falciparum* and *P. ovale* are the most common whereas *P. falciparum* is the deadliest.

1.3. Life cycle of *P. falciparum*

Figure 1 The Life cycle of *P. falciparum* [5] (available at <http://www.cdc.gov/malaria/worldwide/impact>.)

The life cycle of the malaria parasite *P. falciparum* comprises two (2) hosts; humans and mosquitoes, and three (3) distinctive stages; human liver stage (exo-erythrocytic cycle), human blood stage (erythrocytic cycle), and mosquito stage (sporogonic cycle). The exo-erythrocytic cycle commences during the blood meal during which malaria-infected female anopheles mosquito inoculates into the human host the sporozoites. The sporozoites on entry into the human host infect the human liver cells, where they mature into schizonts which rupture and release merozoites. The released merozoites then infect the human red blood cells. This marks the beginning of the erythrocytic cycle. In the red blood cells, the parasite multiplies asexually, some of the merozoites develop into ring-stage trophozoites while some mature into schizonts. The schizonts rupture and release more merozoites while some of the trophozoites differentiate into gametocytes. During a blood meal, the *Anopheles* mosquito ingests the male gametocytes (microgametocytes) and the female gametocytes (macrogametocytes) and this marks the beginning of the sporogonic cycle. Inside the mosquito's gut, the macrogametocytes are penetrated by the microgametocytes giving rise to the zygotes. The zygotes develop into the ookinetes by becoming motile and elongated. The ookinetes permeates the mid-gut walls of the mosquito where they further develop into the oocysts. The oocysts then grow, rupture and release the sporozoites which migrate to the

salivary glands of the mosquito. During a blood meal, the sporozoites are inoculated into a new human host and this continues the malaria life cycle [5].

1.4. Common classes of drugs used in Malaria treatment and their mechanisms of action

The table 1 shows the different classes of drugs used in the treatment of malaria and their various mechanisms of action.

Table 1 Classes of antimalarial drugs and respective mechanism of action

S/N	Class of Drug	Examples	Mechanism of Action
1	Artemisinin and its derivatives	Artemether, Artesunate, Dihydroartemisinin.	Disrupts the malaria parasite's metabolic processes, leading to the death of the parasite.
2	Chloroquine and related compounds	Chloroquine, Hydroxychloroquine.	Inhibits the heme polymerase enzyme, preventing the detoxification of heme, which is toxic to the parasite.
3	Quinoline compounds	Mefloquine	Disrupts the parasite's ability to build essential proteins, affecting its growth and replication.
4	Antimalarial antiprotozoal agents	Atovaquone-Proguanil combination (Malarone)	Atovaquone interferes with the parasite's mitochondrial electron transport chain, while proguanil inhibits DNA synthesis.
5	Sulfadoxine-Pyrimethamine combination	Fansidar, Amalar, Malareich	Sulfadoxine and pyrimethamine inhibit two enzymes involved in the folate synthesis pathway, essential for the parasite's growth.
6	Antimalarial antibiotics	Doxycycline, Clindamycin	These antibiotics interfere with protein synthesis within the parasite by binding to the parasites' ribosomes.
7	Primaquine		Kills the dormant liver stages (hypnozoites) of the parasite, which can cause relapses.

1.5. Resistance patterns found in malaria treatment.

Treatment and complete eradication of malaria has consistently been challenged by the development of resistance to various treatment options by the malaria parasite. Some of these resistance patterns have been identified and efforts to reverse them are still in-process whereas some of the patterns are yet to be understood. Table 2 below shows some of the resistance patterns to antimalarial drugs.

Table 2 Major antimalarial drugs and their resistance status in Africa [6]

	Use	Resistance polymorphisms	Situation in Africa
4-aminoquinolines			
Chloroquine	Treatment of non- <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> malaria	<i>Pfcr</i> 76Thr primary mediator; <i>pfmdr1</i> 86Tyr and 1246Tyr; other SNPs in these two genes contribute, mainly outside of Africa	Resistance, mediated primarily by <i>pfcr</i> 76Thr, has been widespread, but reversion to wild-type (sensitive) parasites is ongoing in many areas
Amodiaquine	Treatment in combination with artesunate	Impacted by the same mutations as chloroquine, but active against resistant parasites	Cross-resistance with chloroquine, but artesunate-amodiaquine is highly efficacious

Bis-quinoline			
Piperaquine	Treatment in combination with DHA	Increased plasmeprin-2 copy number; <i>pfert</i> SNPs	Highly effective in combination with DHA; resistance polymorphisms seen in southeast Asia are uncommon in Africa
Arylamino alcohols			
Quinine	Treatment, including severe malaria	SNPs in <i>pfmdr1</i> , <i>pfmdr6</i> , <i>pfert</i> , <i>pfmrp1</i> , and <i>pfmhe1</i> might be associated with resistance	Parasites generally susceptible
Mefloquine	Treatment or prophylaxis as monotherapy or in combination with artesunate	Increased <i>pfmdr1</i> copy number	Highly effective in combination with artesunate
Lumefantrine	Treatment in combination with artemether	Resistance not documented; decreased sensitivity associated with <i>pfert</i> and <i>pfmdr1</i> polymorphisms	Highly effective in combination with artemether
Mannich base			
Pyronaridine	Treatment in combination with artesunate	<i>pfert</i> 76Thr mutation associated with decreased ex vivo sensitivity	Highly effective in combination with artesunate
Artemisinin			
DHA	Treatment in combination with piperaquine	K13PD mutations	Highly effective as ACT component
Artemether	Treatment in combination with lumefantrine	K13PD mutations	Highly effective as ACT component
Artesunate	Treatment in combination with amodiaquine, mefloquine, or pyronaridine; severe malaria (intravenous)	K13PD mutations	Highly effective as ACT component
Quinone			
Atovaquone	Treatment and prophylaxis, both in combination with proguanil	Mutations in cytochrome b, particularly 268Ser, 268Cys, 268Asn	Resistance has been reported, but uncommon
Folate antagonists			
Pyrimethamine	Treatment in combination with sulfadoxine	Step-wise resistance with acquisition of <i>pfdhfr</i> mutations (108Asn, 51Ile, 59Arg, and 164Leu)	Widespread resistance
Proguanil	Treatment and prophylaxis, both in combination with	Step-wise resistance with acquisition of	Widespread resistance

	atovaquone	<i>pfdhfr</i> mutations (108Asn, 51Ile, 59Arg, and 164Leu)	
Sulfonamide folate antagonist			
Sulfadoxine	Treatment in combination with pyrimethamine	Step-wise resistance with acquisition of <i>pfdhps</i> mutations (primarily 437Gly, 540Glu, 581Gly)	Widespread resistance
Tetracycline antibiotic			
Doxycycline	Treatment in combination with quinine; prophylaxis	SNPs in <i>pfmdt</i> and <i>pftetQ</i>	Unclear if clinically relevant resistance is present
8-aminoquinolines			
Primaquine	Elimination of dormant stages <i>Plasmodium vivax</i> and <i>Plasmodium ovale</i> ; elimination of gametocytes; prophylaxis	Resistance not documented	Little used in Africa; single-dose therapy being studied to control transmission
Tafenoquine	Elimination of dormant stages <i>P vivax</i> and <i>P ovale</i> ; elimination of gametocytes; prophylaxis	Resistance not documented	Newly approved

SNP=single nucleotide polymorphism. DHA=dihydroartemisinin. ACT=artemisinin-based combination therapies.

1.6. Essential oils as antimalarial agents

Several essential oils have been successfully evaluated and identified to possess antimalarial activity. These essential oils present a range of strategies that can be employed in combating the increasing cases of malaria resistance. Ashokkumar *et al.*, reviewed the pharmacological properties of *Myristica fragrans* (Houtt.) essential oil and confirmed that amongst other properties, the essential oils from *M. fragrans* possess antimalarial activity [7]. Tchoumboungang *et al.*, investigated the essential oils of *Cymbopogon citratus* and *Ocimum gratissimum* with the conclusion that both essential oils showed significant antimalarial activities in the four-day suppressive *in vivo* test in mice [8]. Similarly, Mota *et al.*, evaluated the essential oils from *Vanillosmopsis arborea*, *Lippia sidoides* and *Croton zehntneri* and reported the varying degrees of antimalarial activities of the plants' essential oils [9]. The essential oil of *Rhododendron subarcticum* was investigated by Séguin *et al.* [10]

A good number of medicinal plants have been reported to possess antimalarial properties which can provide alternative treatment strategies against malaria parasites.

Ganfou *et al.*, investigated *Acanthospermum hispidum* D.C. use in malaria treatment and reported that crude acidic water extract, fractions and pure isolated compounds from *A. hispidum* show promising *in vitro* antiplasmodial activity [11]. Ethanolic extracts of *Bidens pilosa* L. (Asteraceae) was reported by Andrade-Neto *et al.*, to possess activity against *P. falciparum* drug-resistant parasites *in vitro* and also in rodent malaria *in vivo* [12]. Lusakibanza *et al.*, evaluated five (5) Congolese medicinal plants; *Anisopappus chinensis*, *Physalis angulate*, *Strychnos icaja*, *Entandrophragma palustre* and *Melia azedarach* and concluded that *A. chinensis*, *P. angulate* and *S. icaja* possess very high anti-plasmodial activity *in vivo* [13]. Konziase evaluated the antimalarial potencies *in vitro* and *in vivo* of pure biflavanones from *Garcinia kola* and determined significant *in vivo* antimalarial activities in mice infected with *P. berghei* (ANKA strain) following a four-day suppressive test [14].

Extracts of *Phlomis kurdica*, *P. leucophracta*, *Scrophularia cryptophila*, *Morina persica*, and *Asperula nitida* subsp. *Subcapitellata* were reported by Tasdemir *et al.*, as possessing very potent antiplasmodial activity against the multi-drug resistant K1 *Plasmodium falciparum* strain [15]. Muthaura *et al.*, evaluated ten (10) Kenyan medicinal plants; *Boscia angustifolia*, *Schkuhria pinnat*, *Sphaeranthus suaveolens*, *Clutia abyssinica*, *Ocotea usambarensis*, *Fuerstia africana*,

Ludwigia erecta, *Pittosporum viridiflorum*, *Vangueria acutiloba* Robyns, and *Clerodendrum eriophyllum* with the conclusion that methanolic extracts of all ten plants have varying degrees of *in vivo* activities against chloroquine-sensitive *P. falciparum* clone and resistant clone [16]. Similarly, *in vivo* intrinsic antimalarial activities of methanolic extracts of *Maytenus undata*, *Flueggea virosa*, *Maytenus putterlickioides*, *Warburgia stuhlmannii*, and *Harungana madagascariensis* against chloroquine-sensitive *P. falciparum* clone and resistant clone were determined by Muthaura *et al* [17]. Antimalarial activities of several other plants such as *Croton mubango*, *Nauclea pobeguini*, *Pyrenacantha staudtii* [18], *Eucalyptus globulus* [19], *Azadiracta indica* [20], etc. have been investigated and reported.

1.7. Active compounds in essential oils with antimalarial activity

A list of some active compounds that have been reported to be present in essential oils with antimalarial activity are listed in table 3.

Table 3 Essential oil constituents with reported antimalarial activity

S/N	Active compound in Essential Oils with antimalarial activity
1	α -thujene [10, 21]
2	α -pinene [10, 21]
3	Camphene [10, 21]
4	Sabinene [10, 21]
5	β -pinene [10, 21]
6	1-octen-3-ol [10, 21]
7	Myrcene [10, 21]
8	α -phellandrene [10, 21]
9	δ -3-carene [10, 21]
10	α -terpinene [10, 21]
11	<i>p</i> -cymene [10, 21]
12	Limonene [10, 21]
13	β -phellandrene [10, 21]
14	(<i>Z</i>)- β -ocimene [10, 21]
15	(<i>E</i>)- β -ocimene [10, 21]
16	γ -terpinene [10, 21, 22]
17	Terpinolene [10, 21]
18	<i>p</i> -cymenene [10, 21]
19	Linalool [10, 21]
20	n-nonanal [10]
21	1,3,8-p-menthatriene [10]
22	dehydro sabina ketone [10]
23	cis-p-menth-2-en-1-ol [10]
24	trans-pinocarveol [10, 21]
25	trans-p-menth-2-en-1-ol [10]
26	Camphor [10, 21]
27	Pinocarvone [10, 21]

28	Borneol [10, 21]
29	terpinen-4-ol [10, 21]
30	thuj-3-en-10-al [10]
31	Cryptone [10]
32	Myrtenal [10]
33	α -terpineol [10, 21]
34	<i>p</i> -cymen-8-ol [10, 21]
35	Estragol [10]
36	Myrtenol [10, 21]
37	Ascaridole [10]
38	cis-piperitone [10]
39	carvenone oxide [10]
40	Phellandral [10]
41	bornyl acetate [10, 21]
42	<i>p</i> -cymen-7-ol [10]
43	Thymol [10, 21]
44	Carvacrol [10, 21, 22]
45	Isoascaridole [10]
46	<i>p</i> -mentha-1,4-dien-7-ol [10]
47	citronellyl acetate [10]
48	geranyl acetate [10, 21]
49	Aromadendrene [10]
50	(<i>E</i>)- β -farnesene [10]
51	caryophyllene oxide [10]
52	14-hydroxy-(<i>Z</i>)-caryophyllene [10]
53	Germacrene [10]
54	<i>E</i> - and <i>Z</i> -(\pm)-Nerolidol [22]
55	Linalyl acetate [21, 22]
56	(-)-Pulegone [22]
57	isobutyl isobutyrate [21]
58	1,8-cineole [21]
59	β -thujone [21]
60	1-octen-3-yl acetate [21]
61	α -fenchol [21]
62	α -thujone [21]
63	methyl chavicol [21]
64	lavandulyl acetate [21]
65	myrtenyl acetate [21]

66	citronellyl acetate [21]
67	neryl acetate [21]
68	methyl eugenol [21]
69	β -caryophyllene [21]
70	α -humulene [21]
71	β -farnesene [21]
72	germacrene D [21]
73	γ -cadinene [21]
74	δ -cadinene [21]
75	Ledol [21]
76	benzyl benzoate [21]

1.8. Advantages of essential oils in malaria treatment and combating resistance

The advantages of essential oils in malaria treatment and combating antimalaria resistance are attributed to the wide variety of chemical compositions of essential oils with individualized characteristics and activities. The lifecycle of malaria-causative organisms is comprised of several developmental and maturation stages. Use of essential oils with antimalarial properties has the advantage of multifactorial mechanisms of action by having each or some of the chemical constituents acting at different points of the parasites' transmission, development, and/or infective stages. Papulwar *et al.*, investigated the insecticidal property of *Cymbopogon winterianus* (Lemon grass) essential oil with the key findings that *C. winterianus* essential oil causes deformations in different stages of insect development, repellence, and deterrence. This insecticidal property of *C. winterianus* essential oil can be beneficial in the treatment of malaria by either repelling or killing mosquitoes, the malaria vector [23]. Other attributable advantages of essential oils include low toxicity, high availability, synergistic effects, etc [23].

1.9. Formulation strategies for oral delivery of essential oils

Despite the versatility of essential oils and their associated advantages, they are still prone to a couple of limitations such as high volatility, hydrophobicity, instability and certain degrees of toxicity [24, 25]. Several formulation strategies have been recommended by researchers as a means of overcoming these challenges or limitations. These strategies involve formulating the essential oils into various novel drug delivery systems namely; nano and microemulsions, solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN), liposomes, nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC), nano-capsules and soft gelatin capsules. Terpenes extracted from *Melaleuca alternifolia* was nanoencapsulated by Donsi *et al.*, and demonstrated that the nanoencapsulated terpenes had higher antimicrobial activity compared with the unencapsulated mixture [26]. Sugumar *et al.*, formulated nanoemulsions of *Eucalyptus* essential oil which showed greater antimicrobial activity in comparison with pure *Eucalyptus* essential oil [27]. Clove essential oil-loaded nanoemulsions demonstrated better activity in wound healing than the pure Clove essential oil [28]. Essential oils have equally been formulated as liposomes by different researchers with reported greater activities than the pure essential oils administered as such [29-41].

2. Conclusion

It is the view of the authors that the use of essential oils in the treatment of malaria and combating of malaria resistance hold great promises and potentials; these essential oils when discovered to possess antimalarial activities should be strategically formulated either as a nanoemulsion, liposome, NLC, or SLN. This will in addition to protecting the essential oils from rapid degradation, improve their efficacy and effectiveness.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is to be disclosed.

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